

Enhancing Biology and Chemistry Learning in Nigerian Secondary Schools Through AI Technologies.

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The composites of AI for practical Biology and Chemistry (BAC) involved causal, predictive, and generative types of AI, which have cutting edge capabilities for problem solving in BAC. Integrating AI into the BAC for Senior Secondary Schools was necessitated out of the needs for addressing more intricate issues in BAC practical. The use of virtual labs, AI-powered simulations, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) and virtual dissection tools, had revolutionized how BAC students were engaged with practical without physical apparatus, equipment, specimens or chemicals. The purpose of this study was to investigate how AI-based technologies, would enhance SSS students' BAC practical skills and learning experiences. The population for this study involved all senior secondary school (SSS) students offering biology and chemistry (BAC) in Lagos State, Nigeria. A total of 184 students were purposively selected for the study from six senior secondary schools (SSS) in Education District V of Lagos State. Two research instruments were used for collecting data in this study. The content and face validity of the instruments were established with pilot studies and further validated with the opinions and suggestions of experts of AI, chemistry education and biology education. Cronbach's Alpha reliability test for AIBACPQ gave 0.89 reliability index. Results revealed that AI technologies have promising solutions to the challenges in BAC practical and empower students with innovative skills, which transforms the barriers in their learning experiences. By implications, AI supports BAC teachers' competencies and enhanced students' practical works' engagements, interests, motivation, achievements and learning experiences in BAC.

Keywords

Enhanced Practical Skills, AI, Learning Experiences, Virtual Laboratories, Innovative Skills, Simulation Learning.

Introduction

The use of whiteboards and overhead projectors was the main feature of early classroom technology, giving teachers basic visual aids to supplement lessons (Mhlongo *et al.*, 2023). Artificial Intelligence (AI) has contemporarily transformed school learning, reshaping how students learn, how teachers facilitate it, and how educational institutions operate. AI has significantly transformed and personalised students' learning experiences (Braimoh *et al.*, 2024). Traditional education models often rely on a one-size-fits-all

approach, in which students are taught at the same pace, regardless of their individual learning needs. AI has changed this dynamic by allowing for adaptive learning systems that analyse student performance in real-time and adjust the pace, difficulty, and style of instruction to suit each learner (Ou, 2024; Boussouf *et al.*, 2024; Kumar *et al.*, 2023; Ayeni *et al.*, 2024).

Olaleye and Braimoh (2024) explained how practical skills form the cornerstone of

effective learning experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC) in senior secondary school (SSS) education. The hands-on effects of practical activities equipped SSS students with knowledge beyond theoretical concepts (Ogunmade *et al.*, 2024). The practical activities in BAC engaged students in real-life applications of concepts. Experiments in practical exercises reinforce the understanding of concepts, principles and laws (Olaleye & Braimoh, 2024; Oladejo *et al.*, 2024). Contemporary BAC learning strategies exposed students to new ways of imparting fundamental information, acquiring knowledge and discouraging the memorisation of equations and reactions. Basically, students at their bests grasp the dynamics of scientific reactions when they perform experiments, measure reactants, observe colour changes, and analyse substances. Lameed, *et al.*, (2024) revealed that critical scientific processes, such as observation, analytical reasoning, problem-solving and hypotheses testing were developed with direct involvement and experience. These processes were essential to stimulating students' intellectual curiosity, thereby leading them to investigate more relatable problems within their communities and ignite their lifetime passion for science and leading careers in science-related fields (Chala, 2019).

Practical skills helped students improve their theoretical comprehensions of knowledge and enhanced the application of BAC concepts in real-life situations. The unprecedented learning capabilities of AI would also influence students' internalization of BAC concepts, principles, laws and ideas, which were regularly interpreted into practical exercises in order to enhance their learning experiences. Many principles, laws, theories and ideas in BAC can appear abstract

without the learning strategies or reinforcements provided through practical exercises. Hands-on activities provided by AI systems deepens students' cognitive connection to the subject matter concepts, thereby, making learning more interactive, engaging, retentive and recalled (Lameed, *et al.*, 2024; Shana & Abulibdeh, 2020; Niyitanga *et al.*, 2021). Practical work in AI often involves collaboration between students. Working together in groups to conduct practical fosters essential interpersonal skills such as teamwork, communication, and leadership. These collaborative efforts mirrored real-world scientific practices that prepared students for the cooperative nature of modern scientific research and problem-solving. Practical skills also promote familiarity with data collection, analysis, and interpretation, which were critical components of BAC learning. These experiences prepare students to think critically about scientific and technological developments and are capable of making them navigate and contribute to developing their contemporary world, which is increasingly influenced by AI. There are numerous challenges involved in teaching and learning biology and chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools. Okam and Zakari (2017) reported in the literature that deficiencies in supply of science infrastructure, equipment, materials and resources made it difficult for students to conduct experiments. The literature revealed that poor funding of BAC in Nigerian schools forced BAC teachers to use demonstrations and discussion methodologies to teach the subjects. The challenges associated with practical physical BAC laboratory exercises in Nigerian senior secondary schools (SSS) were further identified by Emeka *et al.* (2021) as follows:

- Lack of adequate funding and resources.
- Shortage of qualified science teachers.
- Lack of facilities and infrastructure.
- Irregular supply of electric power.
- Improper storage facilities; and
- Unethical laboratory safety practices.

According to Mohammed and Watson (2019), the fundamental concept of artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability to accurately mimic the thought processes and behaviours of humans. Olatunde-Ayedun and Hamma (2023) explained artificial intelligence (AI) as a revolutionary technical concept that includes the development of computer systems, which would perform tasks that typically require human cognition. These tasks involve the ability to recognize speech, learn new things, detect anomalies, solve problems, understand natural language processing, and perceive visual data. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a significant traction in school learning and was created as a technological force with capabilities for using cutting-edge technologies to analyze learners' backgrounds, challenges and preferences (Braithmoh *et al.*, 2024), which provides promising potentials for transformation and results-oriented learning in senior secondary school (SSS) biology and chemistry (BAC) learning.

In chemistry education, AI-powered virtual laboratories have emerged as a particularly valuable tool for practical experiments. These virtual laboratories allow students to simulate chemical reactions, measure outcomes, and manipulate variables without the risks associated with handling hazardous substances (Chan *et al.*, 2021). AI-driven platforms provided real-time feedback on students' actions, guiding them through the step-by-step processes in the experiments. Accordingly, Selvam (2024)

and Enebechi *et al.*, (2024) explained that AI technologies have revolutionized how biology students were engaged in practical lessons, effectively using virtual dissection tools powered by AI technologies, which enabled these students to explore the anatomy of organisms without the need for physical specimens. AI technological tools simulated experiences of dissecting animals or observing changes and analyzed results in ways that a highly detailed and interactive, thus, allowing students to zoom in on specific organs, tissues, or structures for better understanding. AI-driven simulations could replicate biological processes such as cell division, gene expression, or enzyme activities, thereby helping students visualize microscopic processes, which are difficult to perceive in a traditional laboratory setting.

The rapid evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) had significantly alleviated the challenges of BAC practical in Nigerian senior secondary schools (SSS). Practical skills are vital for fostering scientific understanding, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities, which are essential for academic success and future careers in BAC-related fields. However, many Nigerian secondary schools encounter a range of systemic barriers, which hindered the effective teaching and learning of BAC practice. According to the West African Examination Council (WAEC), the chief examiner reports for BAC in 2022 and 2023 the following observable weaknesses were made for biology and chemistry:

Biology:

1. Poor spelling of technical terms and one-word answers.
2. Not including magnification of diagrams.
3. Inability to carry out critical observations of specimens.

4. Poor identification of contrasting features when comparing specimens; and
5. Inability to observe and report experiments on food test.

Chemistry:

1. Manipulation of titre value to match those of the teacher.
2. Wrong use of units.
3. Poor mathematical skills.
4. Inability to differentiate between significant unit and decimal points.
5. Improper adherence to qualitative analysis; and
6. Poor knowledge of qualitative analysis.

The integration of AI technologies hold considerable promises for enhancing practical skills in biology and chemistry (BAC). AI has provided innovative solutions that addressed the limitations of traditional laboratory settings by enabling virtual simulations, interactive learning experiences, and personalised educational pathways with AI-powered BAC problem solvers, automated grading and feedback systems (AGFS), hyperwrite chemistry assistance, slides AI, BiologyBuddy.ai, ChatGPT MatDec, duolingo, grammarlythinkster math, otter.ai, audiopen, brainly and canva, gamma etc. (Olatunde-Aiyedun & Hamma, 2023). These virtual experiences made learning of BAC practical and more accessible, which had allowed BAC students to explore advanced BAC topics that may be beyond the reach of their physical laboratories. The solution-based transformative roles of AI technologies did not limit its potentials on enhancing senior secondary school (SSS) students' biology and chemistry (BAC) practical skills and experiences but also equipped them with critical skills needed for their future career and development in BAC

related disciplines. Currently, Nigeria is striving to develop a workforce equipped with necessary transformative skills, which would be required to compete in the global quest for sustainable development (Ogunmade *et. al*, 2024). Therefore, the impetus should be on advancing an increasingly AI driven technology for BAC practical and learning experiences, which would foster an economically productive nation. The purpose of this study is to establish the solution-based transformative roles of artificial intelligence (AI) for enhancing senior secondary school (SSS) students' practical skills and learning experiences in biology and chemistry. The research further investigated SSS students' perceptions about how AI technologies would help to enhance their potentials for developing biology and chemistry (BAC) practical skills and learning experiences

Research Questions

1. To what extent does the use of AI technologies enhance senior secondary school (SSS) students' practical skills and learning experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC)?
2. What are the perceptions of senior secondary schools (SSS) biology and chemistry (BAC) students about how AI technologies enhance their practical skills and learning experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC)?

Theoretical Framework

The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework as explained in Lee *et al.*, (2022) is teachers' contextual knowledge (XK) that described the intersections between technological knowledge (TK), Pedagogical knowledge (PK) and content knowledge (CK).

Pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) is another phenomenon at an intersection. The integration of TK, PK and CK in TPACK is an essential knowledge domain that integrated AI technologies and learning experiences to enhance practical skills in biology and chemistry (BAC). TPACK provides a theoretical understanding of how teachers can effectively incorporate AI tools into their teaching and learning. By combining these three knowledge areas, teachers can create a more engaging and interactive learning environment, thereby addressing both the theoretical and practical challenges (Yeh *et al.*, 2021).

The relevance of the TPACK framework in this study was as follows:

1. It addresses the key challenges facing senior secondary schools (SSS) education in Nigeria, particularly the lack of resources and well-equipped laboratories. By leveraging AI technologies, teachers can overcome these limitations, and by providing students with virtual hands-on experiences they can master biology and chemistry (BAC) practical skills.
2. 21st-century competencies such as problem-solving, critical thinking, deep thinking and data analyses are increasingly technologically driven. The TPACK framework served as a guiding model for how AI technologies could be used to foster BAC practical skills and learning experiences in order to prepare SSS students for future careers in BAC-related disciplines.
3. The TPACK framework encouraged transformative learning in BAC, which is increasingly important as the world becomes more influenced by technological advancements. AI technologies provide interactive and engaging platforms for students to

explore BAC concepts in ways that are aligned with real-world scientific practices.

4. SSS students often lack access to standardized laboratories and quality teachers (Emeka *et al.*, 2021), which affects the quality of learning and results in inequalities in learning outcomes for students. TPACK could potentially democratise BAC practical skills and students' learning experiences, by making advanced learning opportunities more accessible to students, regardless of the availability of school BAC laboratory resources.

The three domains of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) used in this theoretical framework, TK, PK and CK, represented the ability to blend AI technology, pedagogy, and subject matter expertise into cohesive and contextual learning strategies. Thus, TPACK highlighted the importance of how AI technologies could be integrated appropriately into biology and chemistry and how to make learning experiences more interactive, engaging, and effective.

Methodology

The study adopted a mixed-method research design, which combined both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the extent to which AI-based learning technologies would enhance students' learning experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC). The design made the researchers quantify trends and patterns in SSS students' use of AI in BAC, while also gaining deeper insights into the experiences and perceptions of BAC teachers with the use of an interview. The population for this study included all senior secondary school (SSS) students offering biology and chemistry

(BAC) in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample consisted of a total of 184 students from six senior secondary schools (SSS) in Education District V (ED-V) of Lagos State. A purposive sampling technique was used in the study, to ensure that the participating SSS students were volunteers who offered both biology and chemistry and had relevant experiences in the use of AI platforms.

The two research instruments used for collecting data in this study were:

- A self-developed questionnaire titled AI in Biology and Chemistry Practical Questionnaire (AIBACPQ).
- An Interview Protocol (IP).

The Content and face validity of the instruments were established through pilot studies. The researchers also validated the instruments by sorting the opinions and suggestions of five AI experts, five chemistry education experts and five biology education experts. The question items in both instruments were reviewed, to ensure that they adequately covered all relevant aspects of AI integration into biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences. Feedback from the selected experts was used to ensure that the instruments comprehensively addressed the research objectives. Thus, the information from the experts offered helpful responses, which were used to modify and refine the instruments, ensure clarity, and remove any ambiguity that could affect participants' conceptions of statements of the items in the instruments.

The questionnaire - AI in Biology and Chemistry Practical questionnaire (AIBACPQ) was used to assess the Cronbach's alpha reliability. This was done by testing the instruments on 16 respondents who were part of the population but not part of the sample for the study. The instrument has a value of 0.89 reliability index. The Interview Guide was

subjected to an inter-rater reliability technique to determine different raters' agreements with the internal consistency of the instrument. Two independent researchers coded the data. The consistency in their coding was checked to confirm agreement, ensuring the reliability of the thematic analysis.

The structured questionnaire was distributed to the students who constituted the sample for the study. At the end of this, 13 students were randomly selected to participate in the interview. The interview session lasted 12 minutes with each of the respondents. A member of the research team conducted the interview, and video recorded. Data obtained from the AIBACPQ were analysed using descriptive statistics. Measures such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to analyse the quantitative part of the study. The interview data were analysed thematically, with key themes identified to provide a deeper understanding of the extent to which AI-based learning technologies had enhanced SSS students' BAC practical skills and experiences.

Results

This study sought to investigate the role of AI in enhancing SSS students' practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC). Quantitative and qualitative data were collected in the research, in order to achieve the research objectives. Quantitative data were obtained using a structured questionnaire, whereas qualitative data were gathered using an interview protocol. This dual approach allowed for a thorough exploration of the research topics from both numerical and contextual perspectives, thereby enriching the depth and breadth of the findings.

To answer the first research question, which sought to determine the extent to

which AI technologies enhanced senior secondary school (SSS) students’ practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC), frequency distribution and percentage (%) were used to summarize respondents’ opinions for question items of the “AI in Biology and Chemistry Practical

Questionnaire (AIBACPQ).” The participants were requested to respond and base their opinions on each question item on whether they strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed or strongly disagreed. A summary of participants’ answers is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparative level of agreement on how AI learning technologies enhance SSS students’ practical skills and experiences in Biology and Chemistry

S/N	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	AI-based tools help me visualize complex biological processes and topics (e.g. cell division, DNA replication, mendelian genetics, immune system, mitosis & meiosis and nervous system) more effectively than traditional methods.	83 45%	70 38%	13 7%	18 10%
2.	Using AI tools makes it easier to visualise difficult chemistry concepts (e.g. organic reactions, ionisation, chemical kinetics, chemical thermodynamics, redox reactions, stoichiometry, isomerism, quantum numbers, Gibb’s free energy and other energy-related concepts).	105 57%	61 33%	11 6%	7 4%
3.	The virtual labs provided by AI make better learning experiences in biology and chemistry practical.	109 59%	64 35%	7 4%	4 2%
4.	The use of virtual laboratory resources of intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) helps me to perform practical, which our school physical laboratory cannot fully support due to inadequate facilities.	120 65%	49 27%	6 3%	9 5%
5.	AI technologies enable me to conduct biology and chemistry practical without risks associated with handling dangerous chemicals in our school’s physical laboratories.	88 48%	46 25%	24 13%	26 14%
6.	AI-powered simulations would not enhance or support my skills and experiences in biology and chemistry practical.	11 6%	4 2%	44 24%	125 68%
7.	AI technologies would simulate biology and chemistry practical positively and influence my skills and learning experiences.	109 59%	57 31%	9 5%	9 5%
8.	AI virtual labs and dissection tools reduce my dependency on physical laboratories and provide interactive tutorials that improves my biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences.	134 73%	22 12%	13 7%	15 8%

9.	AI tools cannot provide me with analytical and procedural knowledge, which physical laboratories would give for biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences.	18 10%	2 1%	156 85%	7 4%
10.	AI technologies did not foster SSS students' proficiencies in biology and chemistry practical.	11 6%	7 4%	166 90%	-

Table 1 provides a summary of the students' responses to how AI technologies enhance their practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry.

To what extent does the use of AI technologies enhance senior secondary school (SSS) students' practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC)?

Question 1 of AIBACPQ: AI-based tools help me visualize complex biological processes and topics (e.g. cell division DNA replication, Mendelian genetics, immune system, mitosis & meiosis and nervous system) more effectively than traditional methods.

45% (83 students) strongly agreed and 38% (70 students) agreed, showing a high level of positive perception, as a combined 83% of students found AI technologies to be effective for visualizing biological processes. Only 7% disagreed and 10% strongly disagreed. This result indicated that AI technologies support SSS biology and chemistry students to visualize complex biology practical skills and experience. Question 2 of AIBACPQ: Using AI tools makes it easier to visualise difficult chemistry concepts (e.g. ionisation, chemical kinetics, chemical thermodynamics, redox reactions, stoichiometry, isomerism, quantum numbers, Gibb's free energy and other energy related concepts).

Most students (57%, 105) strongly agree, and 33% (61 students) agree, meaning 90% of students believed that AI tools were beneficial to them and that the AI technologies helped them

chemistry (BAC). The interpretation of the results is as follows

Research Question 1

to visualize difficult chemistry concepts. Only 6% disagreed, and 4% strongly disagreed.

Question 3 of AIBACPQ: The virtual labs provided by AI make better learning experiences in biology and chemistry practical.

A strong majority (59% strongly agreed and 35% agreed) supported this statement, which revealed that 94% of the students believed in the virtual labs for enhancing their biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences. Only 6% (combined) disagreed or strongly disagreed with this assertion.

Question 4 of AIBACPQ: The use of virtual laboratory resources of intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) helps me perform practically, which our school physical laboratory cannot fully support due to inadequate facilities.

65% of the respondents strongly agreed, and 27% agreed, making a total of 92%, which felt that AI virtual resources compensated for the deficiencies in the resources of physical laboratories. Very few students disagreed (3% disagreed, and 5% strongly disagreed).

Question 5 of AIBACPQ: AI technologies enable me to conduct biology and chemistry practically without the risks associated with handling dangerous chemicals in our school's physical laboratory.

A total of 13% disagreed and 14% strongly disagreed with this statement, indicating that 73% of the participants showed that AI tools

helped them to avoid risks in biology and chemistry practical.

Question 6 of AIBACPQ: AI-powered simulations would not enhance or support my skills and experiences in biology and chemistry practical.

A large majority (68% - 125 students) strongly disagreed, and 24% (44 students) disagreed with this negative statement, suggesting that 92% believed AI simulations compensate for a lack of reagents or apparatus in practical classes. Only 8% of the participants agreed or strongly agreed with this statement.

Question 7 of AIBACPQ: AI technologies would simulate biology and chemistry practical positively and influence my skills and learning experiences.

Ninety per cent (90%) of the respondents agreed that AI technologies simulate biology and chemistry in situations where chemicals, equipment and materials are limited in supplies. Only 10% disagreed or strongly disagreed.

Question 8 of AIBACPQ: AI virtual labs and dissection tools reduces my dependency on physical laboratories and provide interactive tutorials that improves my biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences.

73% strongly agreed and 12% agreed, meaning that 85% of the students believed that AI tutorials would reduce their dependency on physical demonstrations for practical purposes. Fifteen per cent (15%) disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that some students preferred biology and chemistry conducted in physical laboratories.

Question 9 of AIBACPQ: AI tools cannot provide me with analytical and procedural knowledge, which physical laboratories would give for biology and chemistry practical skills and experiences.

85% of the respondents strongly disagreed with this negative statement, and 4% disagreed, showing that 89% of students believed AI tools

helped them understand complex biological procedures despite equipment limitations. Only 10% strongly agreed or agreed with this negative statement.

Question 10 of AIBACPQ: AI technologies did not foster SSS students' proficiencies in biology and chemistry practical.

The majority of respondents (90%) disagreed with this negative statement, which revealed that they found AI technologies to be helpful in overcoming limitations in chemistry experiments. Only 10% (6% strongly agreed and 4% agreed) felt otherwise.

General Interpretation of the data for Research Question 1:

The results indicated that a high majority of BAC senior secondary school (SSS) students perceived AI technologies as highly effective in enhancing practical skills and experiences of biology and chemistry (BAC). The participants appreciated the ability of AI to compensate for limitations in physical laboratories, such as limited periods and times allocated for practical use, inadequate facilities and use of harmful/dangerous chemicals. The study established that virtual laboratories provided by AI technologies would be more reliable for SSS students' laboratory practice and experiments than what they experience in the contemporary physical laboratories. Data obtained from the "AI in Biology and Chemistry Practical Questionnaire (AIBACPQ)", revealed that AI was crucial for enhancing practical skills and experiences in SSS BAC.

Research Question 2:

What are the perceptions of senior secondary schools (SSS) biology and chemistry (BAC) students about how AI technologies enhance their practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC)?

The second research question sought respondents' perceptions of how AI

technologies enhanced their practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC). In particular, the study pointed the attention of the participants to their perceived difficult aspects of biology, such as cell division, molecular biology, DNA replication, Mendelian genetics, immune system, mitosis and meiosis and nervous system, and to their perceived difficult topics in chemistry, such as organic reactions, ionization and ionization potentials, chemical kinetics, chemical thermodynamics, redox reactions, stoichiometry, isomerism, quantum numbers, Gibb's free energy and other energy related concepts.

Qualitative data obtained from the "Interview Protocol (IP)", were transcribed and organised into three themes.

Theme 1: Improved Visualization and Comprehension of BAC practical and experiences

Many students emphasized that AI technologies provided more vivid and detailed visualization of BAC experiments, which enhanced their practical skills and experiences in biology and chemistry (BAC).

Excerpt of Student Responses:

- Student C: Using AI simulations helped me see the step-by-step in DNA replication and processes. I only read about DNA in textbooks with AI, I can visualize DNA happening in real time, which makes the concept to be much clearer'
- Student E: For organic chemistry reactions, the AI technologies showed organic molecules as they interacted with each other in 3D, which is so much more interesting and motivating than the misconceptions obtained from flat diagrams in textbooks with AI, I can even

rotate the organic molecules and see the reaction from different angles'

- Student F: The innovations and creativity in AI helped us to achieve (timely) results in practical activities I often use virtual labs for my practical works and can work at my conveniences at any time'
- Student A. In the past, I have been struggling with the understanding of mitosis until when I used AI simulations, which showed the different division phases in motion. The process was like in the case of watching a movie, which made it easier to remember and understand.'

Theme 2: Interactive Learning and Engagement with practical skills and experiences

Students found that the interactive nature of AI technology kept them more engaged in learning and allowed them to share their experiences in biology and chemistry practical.

Excerpt of Student Responses:

- Student D: The AI tutorials for organic chemistry reactions, chemical kinetics and chemical thermodynamics allowed me to try out different conditions, like temperature changes, to see how they affect the reactions. The hands-on approach in AI made it easier to understand the theory behind the chemical reactions'
- Student A: In molecular biology, cells division and nervous systems, the interactive quizzes and simulations provided by AI technologies were potentially relevant for our biology practical and helped us to keep carrying out tests by ourselves repeatedly We were particularly motivated and enthusiastic with the leading instructions, corrections guidelines and feedback obtained from AI'
- Student F: The virtual assistance provided by AI prevent time wasting on experiments and helped us to manage tasks Practical

works in AI were automated and helped us to explore different approaches to problem solving'

- Student B: In practical chemistry, the AI software for virtual experiments helped us to make faster decisions in our inferences and decision making the virtual labs gave digital assistances that limits errors in our precisions and calculations'
- Student D: With AI, Instead of just reading how enzymes work, I could easily interact with the system to see how changes in pH or temperature affect enzyme activity'

Theme 3: Overcoming the challenges of resource limitations in physical laboratories

- In environments where physical lab resources were limited, students found AI tools particularly useful for simulating experiments that would have been difficult or impossible to perform in real life.
- Excerpt of Student Responses:
- Student C: Our school does not have the equipment for advanced molecular biology experiments, but the AI lab simulations allowed us to carry out these experiments virtually. It feels like we are working in a high-tech lab'
- Student F: We never had enough chemicals to do organic reactions repeatedly in class, but the AI tool allowed me to simulate multiple reactions without any risk or waste. This makes it easier to understand each step in detail'
- Student A: The AI simulations for cell culture experiments were a game-changer for me. We do not have the proper lab setup, but with AI, I could see how cell cultures grow and behave under different conditions'

Discussion

The findings from both quantitative and qualitative data underscore the transformative

roles of AI-based learning technologies in enhancing SSS students' comprehension of biology and chemistry practical (Braimoh et al., 2023). Quantitative data showed strong positive responses, with 83% of respondents reporting that AI tools improved their ability to visualize biological processes and 90% found AI to be helpful to them in understanding difficult chemistry topics such as chemical bonding and organic reactions. These responses suggest that AI technologies could bridge gaps left by traditional resources, reinforcing cognitive learning through dynamic simulations and enhance visualisations of BAC practical. The results aligned with existing research by Moemeke (2024), Ouyang and Zhang (2024), and Xie (2023), which demonstrated how AI-driven simulations aided grasping science concepts and enhancing learning outcomes. AI tools bridge gaps between theory and application, by allowing students to visualize, explore and interact in BAC processes in a step-wisely manner. The convergence of the findings with previously mentioned highlighted the transformative potential of AI in BAC.

Despite these benefits, some studies questioned whether AI tools can fully replace hands-on laboratory work. Giannakos et al. (2024) noted that while students gained insights from AI simulations, they sometimes faced challenges in transferring these skills to physical labs, where hands-on experiences was crucial. Giannakos et al. (2024) explained the reasons why respondents expressed concerns over AI's limitations in offering tactile feedback or in dealing with hazardous chemicals. The insights in this research indicated that AI, while valuable, should ideally complement rather than replace physical labs to ensure comprehensive skill development. The positive responses also reflect the educational context, in which limited resources make AI an impactful alternative. In Nigeria, many schools face infrastructural

challenges (Emeka et al., 2021), students appreciated AI's ability to overcome practical limitations, and were able to conduct experiments, otherwise unfeasible in their laboratories. Notably, 92% of the students reported that AI tools allowed them to perform experiments despite inadequate equipment or chemicals in their schools. This suggests that AI democratized BAC practical processes by providing equitable access to quality learning experiences, and enhanced engagement and comprehension, irrespective of inadequate physical laboratory facilities and equipment. Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (Rahman, 2024) revealed that AI tools acted as a scaffold, to help students reach higher levels of learning that might not be achievable without additional support. The findings also supported the TPACK frameworks and emphasize the integration of technology (AI) in enhancing students' learning experiences. AI-based tools, served as necessary pedagogical aids that bridged content and engagement, in achieving effective learning experiences. Aligning with TPACK, the results showed that AI technologies not only fill gaps in content delivery but also met students' learning needs, through blended technical knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and content knowledge (CK).

Findings obtained from the qualitative data revealed how AI clarified BAC contents through enhanced visualization, interactivity, and resource supplementation. In this study, many students cited AI's dynamic, step-by-step visualizations as crucial for understanding the intricate learning processes in DNA replication, which they found more accessible than textbook descriptions. This approach aligned with Constructivist Learning Theory (Braithmoh & Olaleye, 2010), which emphasized active engagement and hands-on learning. AI tools provided an interactive environment in which

students can manipulate variables, observe outcomes, and receive immediate feedback, fostering deeper understanding (Braithmoh et al., 2024). AI also delivers a customised, personalised and flexible learning process (Olatunde-Aiyedun and Hama, 2023). Students explore AI simulations to cultivate autonomy and confidence, thereby becoming better motivated and engaged in the BAC learning process. AI tools also address the safety concerns associated with laboratory works. 79 percent of the participants agreed that AI minimized the risks associated with use of dangerous chemicals, indicating that AI simulations contributed to a safer learning environment. This outcome suggested that AI provides controlled and safer alternatives for practical BAC.

Conclusion

In summary, the research demonstrated that AI-based learning technologies significantly enhanced BAC students' practical skills and learning experiences through improved visualization, interactive engagements, and the ability to compensate for physical laboratory limitations. AI tools offer valuable supplementary learning experiences and alternatives to traditional laboratory-based physical practices. These findings align with multiple representation models (Olaleye and Braithmoh, 2024), including cognitive load theory, constructivist learning theory (Braithmoh and Olaleye, 2010) and self-determination theory (Riley, 2016), which emphasized the importance of active, personalised, and visually supported learning environments. In Nigeria, laboratory resources were not available in all senior secondary schools (SSS) (Emeka *et al.*, 2021), and researchers believed that AI technologies would provide promising solutions to the practical challenges in biology and chemistry (BAC) by equipping the SSS with

innovative skills that would transform the barriers in their learning experiences (Saibu *et al.*, 2024). The presumption was that AI capabilities supported BAC teachers' professional practices and competencies, which by implication, enhanced students' learning experiences in BAC practical work engagements, interests, motivation and achievement.

Recommendations

In response to the findings, the researchers recommended that:

1. School Administrators should support BAC teachers to improving their competencies and professional practices in the use of AI to enhance students' learning experiences in BAC practical work engagements, interests, motivation and achievement.
2. BAC teachers should be encouraged to form a community of professional colleagues to share AI resources that would enhance practical skills and improve students' learning experiences in BAC.
3. BAC teachers should leverage the solution-based transformative roles of AI in developing a high-level degree of competencies in applying AI strategies for enhanced students' practical skills and learning experiences in BAC.
4. Teachers should be very close to their students, monitor their learning processes in the use of AI resources, establish good relationships with them, be aware of their learning needs, and be able to reflect on how these needs could be met.
5. BAC students should be made to understand that AI technologies could only assist them in learning but should not be the solely autonomous resources for their learning.
6. All AI-generated resources and learning materials for BAC must be subjected to ethical and cultural considerations and be carefully reviewed and approved based on trustworthiness and transparency.

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